

Entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) showing moderately resistant reaction to sheath blight and their cross reactions to bacterial blight and bacterial leaf streak at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India.

Designation	Sheath blight ^a	Bacterial blight ^b	Bacterial leaf streak ^c
BR 20-28-2	5.3	8	2
BR 51-74-2	5.8	5	3
B 189b-29-4-3-1	5.3	7	3
B 462 b-Pn-1-3	4.5	7	3
IR578-95-1-3	6.0	4	4
IR1514 A-E 562-2	5.5	5	3
IR1704-13-3-2	5.9	8	3
IR2031-238-4-2-2-3	4.5	8	3
IR2058-74-2-1	4.6	6	3
IR2063-65-2-1	5.3	6	3
IR2068-65-3	4.3	9	2
IR2070-210-3-3-4	5.7	6	2
IR2070-439-3-4	5.1	6	2
IR2071-176-1-5-2	4.6	6	3
IR2172-64	5.5	6	2
IR2307-62-4-1	4.2	7	2
IR2328-27-3-6	5.4	5	3
IR2561-58-1	4.5	4	3
IR2562-17-4	3.7	6	3
IR2688-43-4-3	5.8	8	2
IR2755-E2-11-1-4	5.0	5	2
IR2760-E1-33-1-2	5.5	6	3
IR2793-15-2	5.5	6	3
IR2796-95-1	6.0	6	2
IR2844-5-2	4.0	7	3
IR2844-27-2	4.3	6	3
A 12-167-3	5.5	9	3
BW 196	5.4	7	3
Biplab	4.2	5	4
IR2070-423-2-5-6	4.8	6	3
Bahagia	5.3	9	3
IR480-5-9-3	4.9	9	3
Ob 5.677	5.2	8	3
IR20	5.0	6	3
IR2153-26-3-5-2	5.6	6	3
IR1917-3-10-3	5.4	7	3
IRI917-3-19-2	5.1	8	3

^aLength of infection spread in cm.

^bRated on a scale of 0–9; 0 = no infection.

^cRated on a scale of 0–4; 0 = no infection.

extent of infection (total length of the diseased area in cm) was recorded. The entries were grouped tentatively by the following grade system: 1.0 to 3.0 cm, resistant; 3.1 to 6.0 cm, moderately resistant; 6.1 to 8.0 cm, moderately susceptible; and 8.1 cm and above, susceptible.

Only 37 of the entries showed moderate resistance to sheath blight at Cuttack (see table). No entry was graded resistant to sheath blight and no entry was uniformly resistant to sheath blight, bacterial blight, and bacterial leaf streak.

Key to the strains of rice tungro virus. Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi, India.

A ₁	FK 135 shows mottling and no distinct interveinal stripes	M strain
A ₂	FK 135 shows distinct interveinal stripes	S strain
B ₁	Produces distinct narrowing of leaves in TN1	T strain
B ₂	No narrowing of leaves in TN1	
C ₁	Pacita susceptible. Latisail, if susceptible, shows foliar symptoms.	
D ₁	Does not infect Ambemohar 159 and Pankhari 203	RTV ₁
D ₂	Infects both Ambemohar 159 and Pankhari 203	RTV _{2A}
E ₁	Latisail resistant	RTV _{2A}
E ₂	Latisail susceptible	
F ₁	Ambemohar 102 and Kamod 253 susceptible. TN1 severely affected initially but later produces green leaves. If not, at least Pankhari 203 and Latisail show masking of symptoms.	RTV _{2B}
F ₂	Ambemohar 102 and Kamod 253 resistant. No such recovery or masking	RTV _{2B}
C ₂	Pacita resistant. Latisail symptomless carrier	RTV ₄

maintain uniformity in experimental material and procedures. The standard set of differentials that we recommend for the purpose consists of Ambemohar 102, Ambemohar 159, FK 135, Kamod 253, Latisail, Pacita, Pankhari 203, and TN1. The differentials should be individually inoculated at the two- to three-leaf stage. To standardize the method of inoculation for determining strains, we suggest that three adults of the vector leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) that have earlier access to an infected plant for 24 hours be allowed to feed on each test seedling for 6 hours. Data on percentage of infection, extent of stunting, foliar coloration, and reduction of tillering should be recorded at 30 and at 60 days after inoculation.

Screening of IRON against sheath blight at CRRI

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Three hundred twenty-two entries in the International Rice Observational Nursery were grown in the field and inoculated by inserting a sterile stem piece colonized by *Corticium sasakii* inside the leaf sheath when the crop was at maximum tillering stage. Very good infection developed in the entries, indicating that in centers such as Cuttack where humidity is very high, the stem-tape-inoculation method need not be used.

At 15 days after inoculation, the